

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

VOLUME 3, NUMBER 2
JULY, 2023

PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA

P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editorinchief@httckumba.com
Website: <http://www.httckumba.com>

EDITORIAL BOARD

Supervision:

Professor Ngomo Horace Manga
University of Buea

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Akume Daniel Akume, University of Buea, Cameroon

Associate Editors:

Prof. Ebune B. Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Defang Henry, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Lissouck Daniel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Advisory Editors:

Prof. Tabi Johannes Atemnkeng, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Fonteh Athanasius Amungwa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Lyonga N. Agnes Ngale, University of Buea, Cameroon

Members of the Editorial Board:

Prof. Yamb Belle Emmanuel, University of Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Ambe Njoh Jonathan, University of South Florida, USA
Prof. John Akande, Bowen University, Nigeria
Prof. Talla Pierre Kisito, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Rosemary Shafack, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Njimanted Godfrey Forgha, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Nzalie Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Mouange Ruben, IUT University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon
Prof. Boum Alexander, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Patrick Wanyu Kongnyuy, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Tchuen Ghyslain, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Rose Frii-Manyi Anjoh, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Foadieng Emmanuel, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tchinda Rene, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Tabi Pascal Tabot, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Katte Valentine, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Zinkeng Martina, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Obama Belinga Christian Theophile, University of Ebolowa, Cameroon
Prof. Nkongho Anyi Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Cordelia Givechek Kometa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Ngouateu Wouagfack Paiguy, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchakoutio Alain, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Morfaw Bertrand, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tamba Gaston, IUT University, Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Koumi Simon, ENS, Ebolowa, University of Yaounde I
Prof. Ajongakoh Raymond, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ntabe Eric, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Abanda Henry Fonbiyen, Oxford Brookes University, UK
Dr. Luis Alberto Torrez Cruz, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Aloyem Kaze Claude Vidal, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mfombep Priscilla Mebong, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Asoba Gillian, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Bahel Benjamin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Agbortoko Ayuk Nkem, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mouzong Pemi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Orock Fidelis Tanyi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Wanie Clarkson Mvo, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Dr. Molombe Jeff Mbella, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Emmanuel Tata Sunjo, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ndi Roland Akoh, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon
Dr. Kinfack Juetsa Aubin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Kamda Silapeux Aristide, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Roland Ndah Njoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Table of Contents

STUDY AND DESIGN OF A FOUR-PORTS HYBRID SOLAR/WIND DC-DC CONVERTER	1
Boukar Miri ¹ , Aloyem Kaze Claude ¹ , Ajamah Ferdinand ¹ , Tchouga Tchao Yannick ² , Ngouateu paigui ¹	
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND MULTISCALE NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CRACKS IN VISCOELASTIC MATERIALS: APPLICATION TO BILINGA (NAUCLEADIDEERRICHI)	18
Mbelle Samuel Bisong* ^{1,2} , Tawe laynde ³ , Francois Njock Bayock ² , Valeriy V. Lepov ^{4,5} , Pierre Kisito Talla 6	
HARVESTING COMPOUNDS THE EFFECT OF WATER DEFICIT ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF WATER LEAF [TALINUM TRIANGULARE (JACQ.) WILLD.]	42
Dekoum VM Assaha* ¹ , Awasume Clovis Awasume ¹ , Pascal Tabi Tabot ¹ , Priscilla Mebong Mfombep ¹	
GEOLOCATION AND STUDY OF HOUSEHOLD WELL WATER IN RELATION TO CONTAMINANTS AS HEALTH MAPPING TOOL IN KUMBA, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON	55
BAHEL Benjamin ^{1,2} , NGWEM Bayiha Blaise ³ , Bate Esame Bate ¹ , NDIVE Martin Molua ¹ , Lissouck Daniel ⁴ , YAMB Emmanuel ³	
ANTHROPOMORPHISM AND GREEN ECONOMY: A STUDY OF JOHN NKEMNGONG NKENGASONG'S ANCESTRAL EARTH	72
Fomin Edward Efuat (Ph.D.)	
HUMAN EVOLUTION IN AFRICA AND GENETIC VARIATION: A GENETIC HISTORIAN'S INTERPRETATION	92
Forka Leypey Mathew Fomine	
THE PRAGMATICS OF CAMEROON ENGLISH	110
Menge Aaron Tabe	
FORMULATION OF A SNAIL-PROTEIN RICH MAIZE BASE WEANING FOOD (NutriPACK)	122
Samuel Metuge ^{1,2,3} , Asoba Gillian Nkeudem ^{1,2} , Tabe Frida Bawak ¹ , Ngede Laura Senge ¹ , Teh Rene Ning ² , Sumbele Irene Ule Ngole ²	
FORMULATION OF A YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT FROM CORN MILK, SOY BEANS MILK, SKIMMED MILK ENRICHED WITH BANANA FLAVOUR	135
Mateing Cindry, Fidelis Sameh Ebong* ¹ , Asoba. Gilian Mofor ²	

CUSTOMER ATTRACTION AND RETENTION STRATEGIES IN VERY SMALL BUSINESSES: CASE OF BUTCHERIES IN LIMBE, CAMEROON	152
Ndoko Alice Ekoi, Negou Ernest* ² , Nkenganyi Fonkem Marcellus ³	

HUMAN EVOLUTION IN AFRICA AND GENETIC VARIATION: A GENETIC HISTORIAN'S INTERPRETATION

By

Forka Leypey Mathew Fomine
fomineemathew@yahoo.ca
Department of History and African Civilizations
Faculty of Arts
University of Buea

ABSTRACT

A curious aspect of the theory of evolution is that everybody thinks he understands it. I mean philosophers, social scientists, the humanists, and so on. While, in fact, very few people (scholars) actually/really understand it as it stands, even as it stood when Charles Darwin expressed it, and even less as we now are able to understand it. At a meeting of the Linnean Society of London on July 1, 1858, Darwin proposed a theory of evolution by means of natural selection. His monumental treatise, *The Origin of Species*, was published a year later. Darwin's theory revolutionized not only biological thinking, but also politics, sociology and moral philosophy. The weakest part of Darwin's theory was its inability to account for the transfer of biological information from generation to generation. Although it was clear to him that natural selection could be meaningfully defined only in terms of heritable traits, the nature of heredity was poorly understood at that time. All the biological sciences (including genetic history, my own area of specialization) rest on two central principles. One is that all processes have an entire physical and chemical basis. The other is that all organisms and their characteristics are products of evolution. Hence, evolution provides a framework for understanding all the features of living things, and illuminates all the biological disciplines, from molecular biology and biochemistry to philosophy, behaviour and ecology. Evolution has important social implications in the health science, agriculture, conservation and other human endeavours. Moreover, evolution has profound implications for anthropology, sociology and philosophy - in short, for how we view ourselves. Everyone (scholar) should know something about evolution, and for anyone who envisions a career in the life sciences, an understanding of evolution is indispensable. This paper argues that man is an evolved being, a stark contrast of the Christian view that man was created by God according to the book of genesis. The paper further argues that Africa is the cradle of humanity taking into consideration the several archaeological hotspots found in the north, East and South Africa.

Keywords: Human evolution, Africa, Genetic variation, Biology, Ape, Species.

1 Introduction

Humans have inhabited Africa longer than anywhere else on earth. Their history there reaches back beyond the oldest known stone tools to the point, 6 million to 7 million years ago, when the evolutionary lineage that ultimately produced *Homo sapiens* finally diverged from that leading to other hominids. Investigating the human past in Africa is thus crucial to developing an understanding of our origins and history as a species, to answering the question, what makes (and made) us humans? Responding to this challenge, archaeologists have learned that Africa was not once, but three times, humanity's continent of origin: first, as the members of the *hominin* lineage itself, second, as members of the genus *Homo*, which emerged around 2 million years, and most recently with the evolution of anatomically modern humans and their subsequent expansion beyond Africa within the past 100,000 years. Moreover, an emerging body of evidence indicates that distinctively modern forms of behaviour, specifically the constitution of individual and community life through the use of material objects charged with symbolism and socially ascribed meanings, also have their roots in Africa (Berham and Mitchell, 2008).

Evolution is always associated with time. After all, evolution is a process that occurs through time, and it is the extraordinary long stretches of time that are involved that strike the imagination. This paper sets out to illuminate why humans evolved and what the implications of this may be. I believe that humans evolved because of the specific circumstances, in time and space, in which ancient human populations found themselves. This paper therefore argues that the theory of natural selection remains the most powerful mechanism for explaining evolutionary change. In order to understand this mechanism, it is very crucial to take note that in the *Origin of Species* and *The Descent of Man*, Charles Darwin laid out not just another narrative of human origins, but more importantly, a scientific mechanism by which humans could have arisen without the need for human intervention. That mechanism was natural selection. He illustrated convincingly that humans were not the act of a special creation but were instead merely part of a continuum of evolutionary change. Science had, in the shape of evolutionary biology, extended its grasp to the most basic philosophical questions – what human beings are all about.

2 Literature Review

Africa has the longest record – some 2.5 million years – of human occupation than any other continent on earth. For nearly all of this time, its inhabitants have made tools from stone and have acquired their food from its rich, wild plant and animal resources. Archaeological research in Africa is crucial for understanding the origins of humans and the diversity of hunter-gatherer ways of life. Berham and Mitchell (2008) writing in *First Africans: African Archaeology from the Earliest Toolmakers to most Recent Foragers*, provide an up-to-date comprehensive synthesis of the record left by Africa's earliest *hominin* inhabitants and hunter-gatherers. Berham and Mitchell further examine what they have termed the second major event of *hominin* evolution, the radiation of the genus *Homo* 2.3 – 1.0 mya, and consider associated developments in behaviour and morphology.

Alexandre Livingstone Smith and Scott MacEachern (2017) writing in "Introduction: Thinking and writing on the past in Africa, express themselves very explicitly that "while the African continent is generally acknowledged as the cradle of mankind, the general public is rarely aware of events following this almost mythical beginning." They are also of the opinion that the African continent clearly has a past, but knowledge of the past is partial, filtered and sometimes biased. The reason for this denial of history is related to the international slave trade and the politics of colonial expansion, which certainly did not leave much for mutual respect and enlightened exchange, but also to the fact that scientific research in colonial nations was dominated by evolutionist thought.

By the 1960s, Africa was recognised as the source of the earliest human ancestors. Influential physical anthropologists argued that present-day political problems and social dilemmas had their roots in our evolutionary history, and these could be better understood through paleoanthropological field research and comparative primate studies (Gifford-Gonzalez, 2018).

Natural selection explains how and why evolution occurs. Individuals with certain traits survive and reproduce more successfully than individuals with other traits. The genes involved in producing those successful traits are passed on to the next generation in greater numbers. Darwin did not know about genes, but he knew traits were inherited; the modern theory of selection had to await the rediscovery of Mendelian genetics and the synthesis of Mendel's laws with Darwin's theory by early population geneticists' Natural selection leads to adaptation. Genes that promote more optimal use of resources in an environment result in enhanced survival and reproduction of their carriers, and consequently each successive generation becomes more adapted to the environment. When the environment changes, the population will eventually track the changes or go extinct. The environment includes everything: climate, flora and fauna, predators, parasites, and members of one's own species. Our bodies and behaviour have been shaped by competition between individuals in the past, and we all have inherited our genes from the winners of that competition. Sexual selection is the component of natural selection that deals with reproduction. Ultimately, greater reproductive success matters more than longevity because no one lives forever. Even if one lived to be a thousand years old, without reproducing, one's own genes would not be passed on, so one's personal fitness would be zero.

We can see, therefore, why selection should commonly favour individuals who selfishly exploit resources for their own reproductive benefit (individual selection) (Marlowe, 2010).

Another scholar who has tackled the problem of human evolution in Africa is David W. Phillipson (Phillipson, 2005). Phillipson argues that archaeological data provide a picture of the past which is essentially different from, and in many ways complementary to, that which may be reconstructed from written or oral sources. The archaeologist studying the material remains of a pre-literate people will hardly ever be able to learn the names or characters of individuals. He or she will often find it difficult to make more than very general inferences about social systems or political situations. On the other hand, the archaeologist's interpretation of technological skills and economic practices, such as hunting, agriculture or the herding of domestic animals, will generally be far more complete and reliable than that which can be

obtained by other types of research. For this reason it is not just to the study of prehistory that archaeology can make an important contribution; it is also an approach that greatly aids our understanding of more recent societies, even those for which abundant written records are available. To African researchers, the findings of archaeological research represent a major source of information about the continent's past; it is the principal source for most of our understanding of prehistory, and it makes a significant contribution to knowledge about more recent periods. In Africa, the shallow time-depths to which archaeological investigations may often be usefully applied greatly increase our historical perspective of recent trends and events; and it may justly be claimed that our understanding of such pressing contemporary problems as desertification and tribalism is enhanced through the results of archaeological research, with obvious implications for economic and political development. In addition, African archaeology is relevant far beyond its own continent. The archaeologists and prehistorians of other regions have much to learn from the African record, not only from its unparalleled evidence for the earliest periods of human development, but also methodologically.

Writing about *Hominin* dispersals in the old world, Richard Klein argues that: *Homo ergaster* was a largely African species that existed between 1.8–1.7 million and perhaps 700,000 years ago. Our understanding is based mostly on fossils from deposits on the eastern and western shores of Lake Turkana in northern Kenya, which date to 1.8–1.5 million years ago. The dating depends mainly on replicated potassium-argon determinations and is remarkably secure.

The principal specimens are two skulls, nine incomplete mandibles, a partial skeleton, and some isolated limb bones from Koobi Fora on the eastern side of the lake, and a skull and associated skeleton of the "Turkana Boy" from Nariokotome III on the western side (Klein, 2018).

Hartl and Clark (1977) also discuss the importance of evolution in the study of human genetics. According to them, evolution provides a wealth of testable hypotheses for all other branches of biology. Many oddities in biology become comprehensible in the light of evolution. They also discuss the role of mutation and evolution in the study of human genetics. However, they laid emphasis on the relation between genetics and medicine, law, biotechnology, molecular biology, cell biology, sociology and anthropology.

Another author who has discussed the importance of studying human genetics is John H. Gillespie. In his document titled: *Population Genetics: A Concise Guide*, he discusses the interaction between drift and genetic variation and comes to the conclusion that both are important to molecular population genetics and its neutral theory (Gillespie, 1989). He further discusses how mutations introduce genetic variations into populations. Gillespie's work is important in that he lays much emphasis on genetic variation at the molecular level, stressing the important point that the variation between individuals within a species is similar to that found between species. He also lays emphasis on the Hardy-Weinberg law, which describes the consequences of random mating on allele and genotype frequencies.

Cavalli-Sforza et al. (1996) have intimated the importance of DNA in general and that of mtDNA in particular. They reveal that the first polymorphisms examined in

humans for evolutionary purposes were from mitochondrial DNA. They further explain mitochondria as being self-reproducing units contained in all cells of higher organisms (eukaryotes, from fungi to mammals), usually in many copies per cell (up to 10,000 or more). They intimate further that mtDNA are transmitted only by the mother but are present in both sexes. Other scholars such as Elaine Johansen Mange and Arthur P. Mange have also intimated the vital role of DNA in the study of human genetics (Mange and Mange, 1999). They reveal that the female egg carries the X chromosome while the male sperm carries the Y chromosome. This is in connection to this study. In spite of this similarity, the authors have laid much emphasis on cancer and other genetic diseases such as Tay - Sachs disease and others. Douglas J. Futuyma, on his part lays emphasis on the phenotype of an individual organism as being determined by nutrition, temperature, social conditions and many other aspects of its environment (Futuyma, 1998) According to him, individuals of a given genotype vary in phenotype because they have experienced different environmental conditions.

3 Methodology

This study makes use of a qualitative approach. Data was collected not only through documentary sources, but also through oral histories and of course archaeology which is by far the most important of the sources utilized in developing the narrative. Among the archaeological sources explored, the fossil record took the lead. Written documents included published books, book chapters and journal articles.

4 Discussion

4.1 Phylogenetic Relationships of the major groups of living primates

"Light will be thrown on the origin of man and his history." These few words are Darwin's only reference to human evolution in the entire *Origin of Species*. Another twelve years would pass before he published on the subject, in *The Descent of Man, and Selection in Relation to Sex*. But by 1859, when *The Origin of Species* was published, it was already obvious that if humans shared a common ancestry with other species, their closest relatives must be the great apes: the Asian Orungutan (*Pongo pygmaeus*) and the African gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla*) and chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*, the common chimpanzee, and *P. Paniscus*, the pygmy chimpanzee or bonobo). Before *The Descent of Man* was published, Darwin's most enthusiastic supporters, Ernst Haeckel in Germany and Thomas Henry Huxley in England, described evidence for common ancestry with the vertebrates, and with apes in particular (Futuyma, 1998).

There is a widely accepted estimate of the phylogeny of the major groups of living primates based on anatomical and especially molecular sequence data. The sub-order *Anthropoidea* includes the new World monkeys and marmosets (*Platyrrhini*) and the Old World monkeys, apes and humans. The superfamily *Hominoidea* includes the gibbons and the great apes and humans. Traditionally humans (*Homo*) have been placed in a separate family (*Hominidea*) from the Orangutan, gorilla, and chimpanzees' family (*Pongidea*). Thus, *Hominoid* refers to the ape and human lineage, and Hominid to the clade that includes humans, but excludes the apes.

The traditional assignment of humans to a separate family from the great apes might imply that *Homo* diverged from the apes before they diverged from each other. However, abundant molecular data, as well as cladistics analyses of morphological

traits, show that human, chimpanzee and gorilla form a monophyletic clade, sharing a more common recent ancestor with each other than with the orangutan (Goodman, 1963).

The relationships among Homo, Pan (chimpanzee), and Gorilla have until recently been unresolved because of their close molecular similarity. Overall, the DNA sequences of these species differ by only about 1 percent, and even in a rapidly evolving *pseudogene*, they differ at less than 2 percent of nucleotide positions. However, both chromosome features and many molecular studies have now provided the evidence that humans and chimpanzees are sister groups, more closely related to each other than to the gorilla. Most molecular analyses have indicated that Homo and Pan diverged about 4.6-5.0 million years ago. The gorilla lineage diverged from the Homo-Pan lineage about 0.3-2.8 million years earlier (Berham and Mitchell, 2008).

Although the common ancestor of humans and chimps need not have closely resembled either, it surely had many of the anatomical features of chimpanzees and gorillas, since these return so many features of their common ancestor. Thus the common ancestor of humans and chimps was probably a large arboreal African ape, with an opposable big toe, long arms relative to its legs, luxuriant body hair, and an ape-sized brain. It may well have walked on its knuckles, as do African apes today, but surely not on its hind feet only. It lived in groups with complex social relationships among the members, and did not form extended monogamous pair-bonds. Many of these features have long been postulated, but a few have been newly suggested by the recent phylogenetic analyses. More significantly, the distinctive features of our species, especially our brain size, capacity for language, and phenomenally elaborate cognitive and intellectual abilities, have evolved very rapidly. The only direct evidence that might tell us the history of morphological changes must come from the fossil record (Futuyma, 1998).

4.2 Interpreting the Hominid Fossil Record

There is no fossil record of the gorilla and chimpanzee lineages, which is not surprising if the ancestors especially lived, as these species do not today, in most tropical forests, which are uncondusive to fossilization. The only fossils that illuminate the origin and evolution of the hominids are classified, in fact in the Hominidae (Marlowe, 2010).

In certain aspects, the hominid fossil record is excellent and in other ways it is dreadfully inadequate. It provides an unequivocal evidence of general, more or less unidirectional trends in many characters, such as cranial capacity, a measure of brain size. The fossils document mosaic evolution, showing that some features began evolving toward the modern condition before others. They show beyond any doubt that modern humans evolved through many intermediate steps from ancestors that in most anatomical respect were apelike (Simons, 1993).

The earliest fossil hominids are called Australopithecines described from a few localities in South Africa. The earliest known specimens, fragments from Ethiopia and Kenya have been named *Ardipithecus ramidus*. The most extensive and informative early fossil material, from Tanzania and Ethiopia has been named *Australopithecus afarensis*. It includes the famous "Lucy", one of the most complete early hominid skeletons.

These forms perhaps representing a single evolving lineage, have many primitive or ancestral features, indicating that they are not far removed from the common ancestor

of humans and chimpanzees. These features include strong prognathism, a flat cranial base, relatively large canine teeth, long arms relative to the legs, a small brain and curved bones in the fingers and toes. These bones, similar to those of apes, imply that *afarensis* climbed trees. At the same time, the structure of the pelvis and hind limb clearly shows that *anamensis* and *afarensis* were bipedal. Indeed, in 1978, Mary Leakey and co-workers found footprint traces of three individuals in rock formed from volcanic ash at an *afarensis* site in Tanzania. There is no evidence, anatomical or archaeological, that *afarensis* made stone or bone tools (Susman, 1994).

Thus *afarensis*, nonhuman in most respects, had made the first critical step towards the human condition by walking upright on its hind legs. Another important feature of *afarensis* is its dentition, relative to Pliocene hominoids and modern pongids, the cheek teeth are larger and thicker enamel, and the canines are reduced. In later hominids, the canines would become reduced till further.

Following *afarensis* in the late Pliocene in Africa, the number of hominid species, and the relationships among them, have not yet been resolved. There were at least two separate lineages, "robust" and "gracile" australopithecines. The robust forms, often referred to as *Paranthropus*, had large molars and premolars and other features adapted for powerful chewing, they probably fed on tubers and hard plant materials. A key figure in the hominid evolution is *Australopithecus africanus*, a gracile form South Africa that has been dated, only approximately, from perhaps 3.0 Mya to about 2.0 Mya. *A. africanus* differs from *A. afarensis* in only a few features, most notably a greater cranial capacity. Whether *afaricanus* is in the line of direct ancestry of modern humans, or became extinct without issue, is debated. There is no clear evidence that *africanus* made tools (Futuyma, 1998).

4.3 Evolution of Homo

The earliest fossils referred to the genus *Homo*, from Tanzania, Ethiopia and South Africa, range from 1.9 to 1.6 million years ago. They may include two species, but are generally all referred to *Homo habilis*. *Homo habilis* is the epitome of a missing link no longer missing. The oldest specimen are very similar to *Australopithecus africanus*, and the younger ones grade into the later form, *Homo erectus*. Compared with *Australopithecus*, *Homo habilis* more nearly resembles modern humans in its greater cranial capacity, reduced *prognathism* and shorter tooth row. Although the limbs retain apelike proportions that suggest an ability to climb the structure of the leg and foot indicates that bipedal locomotion was more nearly human than that of australopithecines. *Homo habilis* is associated with stone tools referred to as Oldowan technology, and with animal bones which bear cut marks and other signs of hominid activity (Difford-Gonzalez, 2018).

Homo habilis grades into later hominid fossils, from about 1.6 million to about 300,000 years ago, referred to *Homo erectus*. *Homo erectus* grades into *Homo sapiens* later in its history. Most though not all authorities think that *habilis*, *erectus* and *sapiens* are a single evolutionary lineage. In most respects, *erectus* from the middle Pleistocene onward has fairly modern human features - the skull is rounded, the face is steeper and less prognathous than in earlier forms, the teeth are smaller, and the cranial capacity is greater. *Erectus* spread from Africa into Asia (Phillipson, 2005), extending eastward to China and Java. Throughout its range, *erectus* is associated with stone, termed the

Acheulian culture, that are more diverse and sophisticated than the Olduvian tools of *Homo habilis*. The use of fire was widespread by half a million years ago.

Thus, throughout hominid evolution, different features evolved at different rates. On average, brain size – cranial capacity – increases throughout hominid history, although not at a constant rate, and there are progressive changes, from *afarensis* to *africanus* to *erectus* to *sapiens*, in many other features, such as the teeth, face, pelvis, hands, and feet. Although many issues remain unresolved, the most important point is fully/adequately documented: that modern humans evolved from an apelike ancestor (Futuyma, 1998).

4.4 Transition from Archaic to Modern *Homo sapiens* in Africa

Homo erectus and archaic *Homo sapiens* were broadly distributed throughout Africa and Asia by about a million years ago. How these ancient populations related to the different human populations has long been a controversial question. Based on the morphology of fossil specimens, advocates of the multi-regional hypothesis hold that archaic *sapiens* population in Africa, Europe and Asia all evolved into modern *sapiens*, with gene flow spreading modern traits among the various populations (Wolpoff, 1989). According to this hypothesis, there should exist genetic differences among modern Africans, Europeans and Asians that track back to the genetic differences that developed among populations of *erectus* and archaic *sapiens* nearly a million years ago. Thus for example, some genes in European populations today would be descended from those carried by European Neanderthals.

In contrast, the replacement hypothesis, often called the *out-of-Africa hypothesis* (the hypothesis to which I the author of this paper strongly ascribe), holds that after archaic *sapiens* spread from Africa to Asia and Europe, modern *sapiens* evolved from archaic *sapiens* in Africa (Mange and Mange, 1999) spread throughout the world in a second expansion, and replaced the populations of archaic *sapiens* without interbreeding with them to any substantial extent (Smith and MacEachern, 2017). That is, the modern *sapiens* that evolved from archaic *sapiens* in Africa was reproductively isolated from Eurasian populations of archaic *sapiens* – it was a distinct biological species. According to this hypothesis, most of the world's populations of archaic *sapiens* became extinct due to competition, and most genes in contemporary populations are descended from those carried by the population of modern *sapiens* that spread from Africa (Futuyma, 1998).

Among the first molecular studies supporting the replacement hypothesis were those carried out in Allan Wilson's laboratory at the University of California, Berkeley. These workers studied sequence diversity in mitochondrial DNA and calibrated the rate of sequence evolution within the human species by the divergence between humans and chimpanzees. Their estimate of the gene tree coalesced to a single gene copy between 166,000 and 249,000 years ago. The gene tree presented by the Berkeley group implied that the ancestral sequence came from African population. The carrier of this ancestral maternally inherited gene has been called "Mitochondrial Eve" or "African Eve." This is because mitochondrial DNA is strictly maternally inherited in humans (Graur and Li, 2000). If some scholars think that Africa is the mother of humanity then a discussion on the position of Africa in human evolution is very imperative.

4.5 African Hotspots and their role in Human evolution

When we look at the fossil evidence in detail, we do not find hominids everywhere across Africa. They occur instead in relatively small pockets in eastern and southern Africa (Cavalli-Sforza, Menozzi, and Piazza, 1996). Those of North Africa are extremely tiny but very significant. The East and South African sites are located in two distinct geological features.

The first and most dramatic of these is the Great African Rift Valley. This is one of the geological wonders of the world. Essentially it is a line of tectonic stress - that is, where two plates of continental matter are tearing apart - that runs from the Luangwa valley in Zambia up through Tanzania, Kenya and Ethiopia to the Red Sea, where it divides and continues on the one hand out into the Indian Ocean and on the other along the Red Sea and into the Jordan Valley. Over the last 20 million years or so the areas to either side of this fault line have been moving apart, and as they have done so, the land in between has dropped down into a valley. In fact it is not a single valley, but a mass of smaller fault scarps where the land has moved up and down. It has created a complex landscape of cliffs and lake basins, dotted with volcanoes. It is among the most active terrestrial landscapes in the world. It is within these lake basins that the best hominid fossil record lies. The fossils are found in the lake and river sediments that have built up. Because of the extensive tectonic movements these have been piled high, and then subsequently exposed by further movements of the earth. The gentle build-up of the lakes, within which animals are buried and preserved, is ideal for fossil formation, while the constant shifting of the strata makes it easy for the palaeontologists subsequently to find them eroding out of the scarps. Amongst these are the hominids of the last 5 million years. The other fossil-rich area is in the Transvaal of South Africa. This is a very different geological context, consisting of ancient limestones that stretch back to the Mesozoic (Futuyma, 1998). These limestones have in places been dissolved out into subterranean caverns, some of which have been exposed by erosion. Into these caverns and holes have fallen the detritus of the millennia - rocks and mud and the bones of animals, including hominids.

The point here is that these are areas that are not necessarily good places to live and to evolve, but good places to die. (Good, that is, if you want to become a fossil). Far more is known about these regions in the past, not necessarily because these areas were richer in ancient hominids and other animals, but because they preserved them in ways that the deserts to the north or the rainforests to the west did not. In these other regions whole communities could evolve and become extinct without anyone knowing anything about them simply because they lived 'in environments in which fossils stand a poor chance of survival (Foley, 1998).

Knowledge of human evolution, therefore, is determined not by evolutionary reality, but by geological accident. It is distorted through the probability of survival after death, not survival of the fittest during life. Perhaps, the African story which I am narrating seems an illusion. Across countless others are as hominids may have scurried their way through their evolutionary lives in ways quite different, and the

African hominids we know of may have been nothing more than peripheral characters with walk-on parts only (ibid).

To some extent this is unlikely to be entirely the case. The evidence of molecular biology seems to indicate that Africa is central, even if the areas that have yielded the fossils may not have been the only ones in which hominids lived. Chimpanzees and gorillas, the most probable sister branch to the ancestral hominids, live across central and western Africa. A look at the distribution of the earliest hominid fossils shows that these extend that distribution in an eastward direction, across into the Rift Valley. Hominids are therefore the eastern branch of the other African apes. This extension takes them not only eastwards but also into more arid environments, away from the less seasonal tropical forests and into the savanna woodlands and grasslands. At the time in question - sometime after 7 million years ago - these were just taking their present shape. The process of rift formation was probably as part of this, along with a general deterioration in the climate. This emerging environment is one that is likely to have imposed entirely new selective pressures on these eastern apes, pressures that would have made a more terrestrial way of life beneficial - hence, perhaps, the evolution of bipedalism. Geographically, therefore, the distribution of the earliest fossils, while being a product of a geological accident, makes sense of the evolutionary patterns as well (ibid).

There is perhaps something more to this than just contiguous geography. The Rift Valley is markedly different in terms of physiography and ecology from the rest of Africa. The constant tectonic upheavals, the eruptions of volcanoes and the deposition of great beds of lava and ash had the effect of cutting up the landscape into a series of relatively isolated lake basins. Throughout the last ten million years this may well have been a most dynamic landscape. More importantly, perhaps, the lacustrine structure would not only have provided an interesting set of ecological circumstances for these exploratory bipedal apes, but would also have divided them up into isolated populations. It is a well-known fact in evolutionary biology that new characteristics are more likely to be promoted and preserved in small populations. In large populations novelty will become swamped and lost, unable to overcome the genetic inertia. Small populations allow for novelty to survive. The fragmented environments of the eastern Rift Valley may thus have created evolutionary hotspots, not just for hominids, but also for many other species. Among the lakes and ashes diversity could flourish, and it is perhaps no coincidence that it is there that we find the earliest radical departure from ape morphology in the form of bipedalism, the greatest number of hominid forms, and, rather more speculatively, even later the emergence of modern humans (Futuyma, 1998).

African hotspots and fossil sites are more impressive and more in number than those found in any other continent. East African fossil sites include: Singa, Hadar, Middle Awash: Belohdie and Maka, Melka Kunture, Omo Valley, West Turkana: Lomekwi and Nariokotome (Klein, 2018), Fejij, Lothagam, Lainyamok, Lake Baringo, Chemeron, Tabarin, Benninj, Kanapoi, Uraha, Laetoli and Udduvai Gorge. Those of South Africa include: Makapansgat, Swartkrans, Komdrai, Taung, Sterkfontein, Border Cave,

Klasies River and Saldanha while the few of north Africa are: Thomas Quarries, Jebel Irhoud, Sale, Toghennif and Haua Fteah. These fossil sites are an apparent indication that man could not evolved elsewhere out of the African continent (Phillipson, 2005).

The African ecological community is the setting for hominid evolution. At the time that the hominids were at their most diverse, many other types of mammal were also radiating into different forms. Today, there are just three type of pig in Africa – the warthog, the bush-pig and the giant forest pig. Two million years ago there may have been over twenty species. The lion and the hyena are at present the only carnivores capable of hunting large prey. Two million years ago there were probably about ten species of large carnivore, some much larger than lions. The same pattern can be seen in a whole host of animals – antelopes, rhinos, elephants as well as closer relatives such as the baboons. Each of these groups reached maximum evolutionary diversity at about the same time (Foley, 1998).

4.6 The fundamental characteristics of Human Beings or what human beings are all about

Humans are descended from something like an ape (Phillipson 2005), and yet they are significantly, perhaps irrevocably different. Humans have developed a subtle and powerful brain. That brain is one of the symbols of the difference between humans and the rest of the animal kingdom. It is several times larger than it should be, and it is clearly essential to human survival and evolutionary success. The modern human brain is approximately 1400 grams in weight. In general, brain weight is closely related to the overall body weight of an animal, and were humans to have the size of brain expected for an animal of our size, it would be about 500 grams.

The large brain undoubtedly facilitates a wide range of distinctively human abilities. Most obvious is linguistic skill. Humans can utter a vast array of sounds, but more importantly, they can order them using diverse and flexible rules, and they can understand the meanings, overt and implicit, of those sounds. Humans can create images in any number of media, and again, give order to them. Human society is based on complex networks of social and economic interaction – co-operation, competition, dependence, altruism, friendship and enmity.

Living humans are characterized by a number of universal features. These underpin the fact that despite some superficial differences both within and between populations, all humans belong to the same species – that is they are all capable of interbreeding and producing viable offspring under normal conditions. They also attest to a common evolutionary origin. Many of these features are simply observable in terms of anatomy. Humans are bipedal, that is they walk in an upright manner on two rather than four limbs. Bipedalism is probably the most physical obvious human feature. It is unique among primates, and it is an adaptation that has had a pronounced effect on the entire musculo-skeletal system. To accommodate this form of locomotion the lower limb has been elongated and strengthened, the foot arched and buttressed and the grasping ability found in other primates lost.

The pelvis has become shortened, rounded and flared to act as a primary support for the upper body. The vertebral column has become curved and strengthened in the

lumbar region. The head is set vertically upon the vertebral column, with the hole through the spinal cord passes to the brain being relocated at the base of the skull instead of towards the back (Foley, 1998).

Bipedalism may have made possible a number of other human features, in particular manual dexterity. Humans along with other primates have grasping, sensitive, five-fingered hands. Most primates are capable of high levels of manipulative dexterity, but this is found in its most extreme form among humans, who have thumbs that are capable of opposing virtually any of the other digits.

Other anatomical features are also striking. Humans have very large brains (as it has already been mentioned above) for their body size, and faces that have become reduced and flat. The hair over most of our bodies is miniaturized, and the skin therefore exposed. Humans also have a potential for copious sweating.

The other distinctive characteristics of human structure lie in the reproductive organs and secondary sexual characteristics. Although modern humans are only moderately sexually dimorphic in terms of size – on average females are about 84 percent the size of males – there are quite marked secondary characteristics. Females have in the dry terminology of the comparative anatomists, pendulous breasts, and more rounded and fleshy buttocks. Physiologically they generally have large fat deposits that they can draw upon during periods of nutritional stress – food insufficiency. Men are generally more hirsute, although this varies in extent from population to population. It is perhaps also reassuring to know that the male human penis is large compared with the other apes, although the testicles are compared with a chimpanzee at least, not especially large.

A whole suite of behavioural characteristics can of course be found in humans and a claim made for their uniqueness. Not surprisingly, many of these have been selected as the features that made humans the way they are. Man the tool-maker, man the hunter, woman the gatherer, *Homo economicus*, *Homo hierarchicus*, *Homo politicus*, and *Homo loquans*. These are all sobriquets that have been designed to epitomize human nature. They and several others are all traits that have been used by various people (scholars) to identify the driving force that underlies human nature.

To many, tool-making has been the decisive factor. Even a cursory glance at the world shows that humans depend on technology to an extraordinary extent. This is not just the case for urban, industrial peoples, but for all societies. Houses, food, weapons, games, all involve technology to some extent even if they are relatively simple in construction. It is hardly surprising especially when humans are compared with other animals, that it has been suggested that this is the key trigger to human success. The basis for tool making emanates partly from the manipulative skills of dexterous hands and partly from the ability of the brain to co-ordinate and create actions that have technological consequences (Renfrew and Bahn, 2016).

4.7 Genetic Polymorphisms and Natural Selection

Our knowledge of human genetics is growing explosively as geneticists use molecular methods to identify and sequence genes, identify gene products and their functions, and identify the mutations that may impair those functions. To facilitate the growth of such knowledge, geneticists throughout the world are contributing to the Human

Genome Project, an effort initiated in 1989 to sequence all 3 billion base pairs, including perhaps 100,000 functional genes, in the human genome.

The causes of a few human polymorphisms are known in part. The best understood are the several variant hemoglobins, such as those causing sickle-cell disease (Mange and Mange, 1999) and lassemia that despite their severally debilitating effects in homozygous condition, are maintained because heterozygotes have heightened resistance to malaria. The same is true of a mutant causing a deficiency of G6PD (glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase), which causes hemolytic anemia in 400 million people worldwide if they ingest certain foods or suffer certain infections, but which greatly reduces the risk of malaria in heterozygotes. In other cases, mutant alleles have high frequencies for unknown reasons, but are potentially subject to natural selection. For example, a deletion in the CRC-5 chemokins receptor gene, which has a frequency of about 0.10 in Caucasian populations, seems to confer resistance to the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) the cause of AIDS by blocking its entrance into cells. However, the spread of HIV is much too recent to account for the high frequency of this allele. In yet other cases, such as the highly variable major histocompatibility gene complex (MHC) the high degree of sequence divergence among haplotypes implies that the polymorphism is very old and thus has been maintained by balancing selection, but the agents of selection are unknown (Futuyama, 1998).

At this stage, we may turn to discuss natural selection and its implications in Human evolution. For us to better appreciate this, it is imperative to pose the question: Is the human species continuing to evolve? To answer this question plausibly, we need to know how the two major agents of allele frequency change, genetic drift and natural selection, are acting now and are likely to act in future.

Until the advent of agriculture, humans subsisted by hunting and gathering (Berham and Mitchell, 2008). Based on the study of the few contemporary populations with this mode of life, it is likely that population density was low and that most populations consisted of rather small groups whose travels were quite localized. Confined by topographic barriers that we today can surmount in hours, such populations would have diverged by genetic drift at nearly neutral loci. Much of the geographic variation in the human species is undoubtedly a consequence of this population structure. Even today, many agricultural populations are highly sedentary. Allele frequency differences have been discerned, for example, among villages along the shore of Lake Atitlan in Guatemala.

The development of ever more complex culture and technology over the last 10, 000 years or more has reduced mortality from many agents that must have afflicted our remote ancestors, and thus has reduced the intensity of natural selection on many characters. Modern technology, education, medicine and especially improved sanitation have greatly reduced pre-reproductive mortality in industrialized nations, reducing the opportunity for natural selection.

Many conditions such as near-sightedness that would have increased the risk of death for our hunter-gatherer ancestors can now be remedied by medical or technological means, such as eye glasses. Phenylketonuria, caused by a recessive mutation, no longer need cause mental retardation and death, it is cured by prescribing a diet without amino acid phenylalanine. However, purifying selection still acts on mutations that

cause pre-reproductive mortality, such as those responsible for cystic fibrosis. And it is important to bear in mind that vast numbers of people worldwide lack money, education, and access to health care, and so are subjected to potential natural selection that are greatly attenuated in affluent, industrialized societies (Futuyama, 1998).

A scientific discussion on natural selection in 2023 will be very incomplete if we leave out the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. When COVID-19 was acknowledged to have arrived Africa in late 2019, politicians, public health authorities and later scholars, scrambled to find appropriate and effective response to the unprecedented pandemic. The pandemic did not only disrupt trans-border movements, in many communities, closure became the default norm. While the virus killed people worldwide, some people in Africa did not only refuse to wear face masks and respect social distancing, they vehemently refused to take the vaccine and until this day, they have never been affected by the devastating pandemic. To the best of my knowledge, though a citizen scientist, this is an excellent example of natural selection as some people died of the virus and a substantial number survived without precautions.

4.8 Evolution and Human Society

Evolution is central to modern biology and to the use of biology in the modern society. Knowledge, principles and methods that have been developed in the study of evolution are used to improve crops and domesticated animals, to combat agricultural pests and human pathogens, to study inherited diseases, to find useful natural products, and in many other applications. From a philosophical point of view, surely little can be more satisfying than to have attained an understanding of our origin and that of other living beings, and to assert with Darwin, that “there is grandeur in this view of life” in which “from so simple a beginning endless forms most beautiful have been, and are being “evolved.”

But knowledge, and the power that comes with it, can be used to our detriment as well as to our good. Herbert Spencer, a contemporary of Darwin promulgated the philosophy of “Social Darwinism, “the doctrine that human progress is the outcome of competition and struggle among individuals, races, and nations, just as” the survival of the fittest” – Spencer’s term for Natural Selection – is the engine of evolutionary “progress.” Spencer opposed state aid to the poor, state support for education, and regulation of business as barriers to competition and therefore to progress. Social Darwinism was immensely popular in the early twentieth-century America, especially among business giants such as John D. Rockefeller (Hofstadter, 1955). Moreover, it went hand in hand with the common belief that intelligent, criminality, and other traits were genetically fixed and could not be altered by the environment. These beliefs led to a flourishing eugenics movement in the first few decades of the century, which advocated encouraging “superior” people to have more children and discouraging “inferior” people from reproducing. Likewise these beliefs were used to justify racism, colonialism, and domination of some people by others.

The risk that evolution and genetics will be abused continues. The hypotheses and data of socio-biology, evolutionary psychology, and human genetics developed largely out of scientist’s quest for intellectual understanding, not out of any desire to justify social norms. But there are elements in the larger society who would use genetic

data to discriminate in employment, who would use heritability to justify social and economic inequality, who would invoke sociobiological hypotheses to deny gay people equal rights and to keep women in the kitchen. Evolutionary scientists, do not set social policy, but they can and perhaps should bear responsibility for alerting the public to the uses to which their discoveries might be put. They can point out misunderstandings and illogical interpretations of evolutionary theory, such as the naturalistic “fallacy” – the belief that what is natural is good, and therefore provides moral guidance for human conduct. Social Darwinism was based on this fallacy. So is the belief that women should be subservient to men because sex roles may have an evolutionary origin (Futuyama, 1998).

There exists no philosophical or scientific foundation for the belief that human behaviour should conform to natural laws. Natural laws like the laws of gravity or natural selection, are simply regulations in the mechanical processes of nature, not rules of conduct. Darwin’s great defender, Thomas Henry Huxley rightly said that cosmic evolution may teach us how the good and evil tendencies of man have come about but, in itself is incompetent to furnish any better reason why what we call good is preferable to what we call evil than what we had before.

Evolutionary biology like other knowledge can serve the cause of human freedom and dignity. Together with those of the other biological sciences, its applications in health science, food production, and environmental management can help to relieve diseases and hunger. It helps us to appreciate both the unity and diversity of mankind. And as we reflect on our common origin with other forms of life, we may even come to feel at one with and to care for those endless forms.

5 Results

Human beings are too complex by their very nature to be studied and understood from the narrow perspective of biology or of any other single academic discipline. Consequently, it is by giving human study a holistic perspective that we can have a mastery of human evolution, human behaviour and human activities. Humans evolved in Africa because of the specific circumstances in time and space in which ancient human populations found themselves. The various archaeological hotspots found in the Africa continent attest to this. African hotspots and fossil sites are more impressive and more in number than those found in any other continent. Prominent East African fossil sites include: Singa, Hadar, Middle Awash: Belohdie and Maka, Melka Kunture, Omo Valley, West Turkana: Lomekwi and Nariokotome, Fejj, Lothagam, Lainyamok, Lake Baringo, Chemeron, Tabarin, Benninj, Kanapoi, Uraha, Laetoli and Udduvai Gorge. Those found in South Africa are: Makapansgat, Swartkrans, Komdrai, Taung, Sterkfontein, Border Cave, Klasies River and Saldanha while the few of north Africa are notably: Thomas Quarries, Jebel Irhoud, Sale, Toghennif and Haua Fteah. These fossil sites are an apparent indication that man could not evolved elsewhere out of the African continent.

This study has also revealed that living humans are characterized by a number of universal features. Many of these features are simply observable in terms of anatomy. Humans are bipedal, that is they walk in an upright manner on two rather than four limbs. Bipedalism is probably the most physical obvious human feature. It is unique

among primates, and it is an adaptation that has had a pronounced effect on the entire musculo-skeletal system. By being bipedal, humans are fit to move on their feet while holding objects with their hands. Also by moving upright, the surface of the human body exposed to direct sunlight is reduced tremendously. Humans can also use their hands to defend themselves while moving upright. This was impossible when ancient humans crawled.

Bipedalism has made possible a number of other human features, in particular manual dexterity. Humans have grasping, sensitive, five-fingered hands. They have thumbs that are capable of opposing virtually any of the other digits. Other anatomical features are also striking - humans have very large brains and their faces have become reduced and flat. The pelvis are shortened, rounded and flared to act as a primary support for the upper body. The vertebral column is curved and strengthened in the lumbar region. The head is set vertically upon the vertebral column, with the hole through the spinal cord passes to the brain being relocated at the base of the skull instead of towards the back.

The other distinctive characteristics of human structure lie in the reproductive organs and secondary sexual characteristics. Although modern humans are only moderately sexually dimorphic in terms of size - on average females are about 84 percent the size of males - there are quite marked secondary characteristics. Females have pendulous breasts, and more rounded and fleshy buttocks. Physiologically they generally have large fat deposits that they can rely upon during food shortage. Men on their part are generally more hirsute, although this varies in extent from population to population. It is perhaps also important to note that the male human penis is larger compared with those of the other apes, although the testicles are compared with those of the chimpanzee.

6 Conclusion

International understanding of the African past has increased and improved enormously during the past one hundred, more particularly the past fifty, years. This understanding extends both throughout the continent itself and far beyond, so that Africa's contribution to the whole story of human development and achievement is coming into focus. This is a matter for celebration, not for ignorance or doubt and backward-looking criticism. It is a story to which the contribution of archaeology is paramount and which needs to be told and understood both in Africa and in world-wide contexts (Phillipson, 2005). This paper has provided an up-to-date synopsis and interpretation of both the archaeological and genetic evidence for the past of humans in Africa from their first appearance up to recent times. The paper has therefore illuminated evidences that it was in Africa that humankind first evolved, during the periods between 5.0 and 2.5 million years ago. At the other end of the time scale, the earliest written records relating to Africa, those of the ancient Egyptians, began about 5000 years ago, for many other parts of the continent, notably the interior regions south of the equator, no such records are more than one or two centuries old.

The strangest revolution in science is the Darwinian one. According to the conventional story, the publication of the *Origin of Species* by Charles Darwin in 1859 led to a stormy but brief battle between religion and science, with evolution

triumphing rapidly over creation to become the orthodoxy. Whereas before, philosophers, theologians and scientists as well as the great majority of educated had believed in the fixed and immutable nature of creation,

The significance of human evolution will vary from one person to another. An anatomist will have different concerns from a zoologist, and a zoologist will differ again from an anthropologist. An anatomist might be particularly concerned about the point at which there is conflict between pelvic outlet size and neonate head-size. A zoologist might be interested in the relationship between the level of behavioural differences and genetic distance in various species including humans, while a social anthropologist might want to know where the term culture becomes appropriate. Whatever the concern humans are most closely related to gorillas and chimpanzees. And almost certainly share their most recent common ancestor with the chimpanzees. Overall, humans and chimpanzees are about 99 percent identical in DNA sequence, and probably diverged about 4.6-5 million years ago.

The oldest known fossil hominids date from the early Pliocene (4.4. Mya) of Africa. Early hominids had several apelike features, including adaptations for climbing trees, but were at least partly bipedal. Other human features evolved later, including a fairly gradual increase in brain size. Several hominid species inhabited Africa until about 1 million years ago. One of them, *Homo habilis* is the first known tool maker. Its apparent descendant, *H. erectus*, spread from Africa into Europe and Asia about 1 million years ago, and evolved into archaic *Homo sapiens*.

Some, but not all study of DNA sequences suggest that modern *Homo sapiens* spread out of Africa in a second wave of dispersal 0.4 and 0.15 million years ago, and replaced populations of archaic *H. sapiens* without interbreeding with them. This dispersal pattern if confirmed would account for the high degree of genetic similarity among all modern human populations. Although there exist allele frequency differences among populations, most of the genetic variation in the human species can be found within any one region. This is a natural human condition of living. Evolutionary biology indeed has much to say about this human condition but so do anthropology, and sociology, Psychology and history, Philosophy and the arts, Genetic history inclusive. Human beings are too complex to be understood from the narrow perspective of biology or of any other single academic discipline. A plausible conclusion of this paper is that hominid evolution is too complex to be reduced to a single evolutionary event and a single directional trend. Among the group that can best be referred to as hominids there is considerable diversity in form and behaviour. Furthermore, modern humans represent just the final fraction of the overall picture. The pre-humans represent more than just the process of becoming human. What, though, do they represent, and what can they imply about the origins of our own species and the process of evolution itself. This question, and in particular the issue of whether human evolution does show progressive trends can also be investigated.

7 References

Books

- Berham, L. and Mitchell, P., (2008), *First Africans: African Archaeology from the Earliest Toolmakers to most Recent Foragers*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Cavalli-Sforza, L. L. Menozzi, P. and Piazza, A. (1996) *The History and Geography of Human Genes*, Princeton, Princeton University Press.
- Foley, R. (1998). *Humans before Humanity: An Evolutionary Perspective*, Massachusetts, Blackwell Publishers Ltd.
- Futuyma, D. J. (1998) *Evolutionary Biology*, Third Edition, Sunderland, Massachusetts: Sinauer Associates, Inc. Publishers.
- Gifford-Gonzalez, D., (2018), *An Introduction to Zooarchaeology*, Cham, Springer International Publishing A.G.
- Gillespie, J. H. (1989), *Population Genetics: A Concise Guide*, Baltimore and London, The John Hopkins University Press.
- Graur, D., Li, W-H. *Fundamentals of Molecular Evolution*, second edition Sunderland, Sinauer Associates, Inc. Publishers.
- Hartl, D. L. Clark, A. G. (1977) *Principles of Population Genetics*, Third Edition, Sunderland, Massachusetts, Sinauer Associates, Inc. Publishers.
- Hofstadter, R. (1955). *Social Darwinism in American Thought*, Boston, Beacon Press.
- Mange, E. J. , Mange, A. P. (1999) *Basic Human Genetics* second edition, Sunderland, Massachusetts, Sinauer Associates, Inc. Publishers.
- Marlowe, F. W., (2010) *The Hadza: Hunter-Gatherers of Tanzania*, California, University of California Press.
- Phillipson, D. W. (2005), *African Archaeology*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Renfrew, C, Bahn, P. (2016). *Archaeology: Theories, Methods and Practices*, seventh edition, London, Thames and Hudson Ltd.

Book chapters

- Goodman, M. (1963) "Man's place in the Phylogeny of primates as reflected in serum proteins." In S.L. Washburn (ed.). *Classification and Human Evolution*, pp. 204-234 Aldine, Chicago.
- Klein, R., (2018). "Hominin Dispersals in the Old World" in *The Human Past: World Prehistory and the Development of Human Societies*. Ed. By Chris Scarre, fourth edition, London, Thames and Hudson Ltd.
- Smith, A. L. and MacEachern, S. (2017), "Introduction: Thinking and Writing on the Past in Africa" in *Field Manual for African Archaeology*, Tervurem, Royal Museum for Central Africa.
- Wolpoff, N. (1989) "Multiregional evolution: The Fossil alternative to Eden" In P. Mellars and C. Stringer (ed.) *The Human Revolution*, pp 62-108, Princeton, Princeton University Press.

Articles

- Simons, E. L. (1993). "Human Origins" *Science* 245: 1343-1350.
- Susman, R. L. (1994). "Fossil Evidence for early hominid tool use", *Science* 265: 1570-1573.